

Effects of Information Load and Pragmatic Load on the Hypo-Hyper Continuum

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Abstract

Stance-taking (pragmatic load) and linguistic surprisal (informational load) have both been shown to modulate the hyper-articulated-reduced continuum in speech; however, the extent to which these factors interact with one another has not been investigated. In this study, we examine two measures of hyper-articulation, vowel space expansion (repulsive force) and vowel duration, in the context of high informational and high pragmatic load, operationalized as lexical surprisal and stance-taking strength. We find that surprisal and stance-taking have significant effects on the repulsive force in the vowel space, with significant interactions between surprisal and stance strength. While both factors affected vowel duration, the evidence for interactions between them is less clear. We interpret the observed hyper-articulation in the context of Lindblom's 1990 H&H theory.

Introduction

The speech signal has many parallel channels of information including pragmatic, sociolinguistic, discourse, lexical, indexical, etc., each of which can affect the degree of reduction/hyper-articulation depending on the speaking context. Previous work (e.g., Freeman, 2014) has shown that strong stance-taking, a dimension of pragmatic load, motivates hyper-

articulation. Similarly, there are well-known findings that words which are less predictable from the speaking context (i.e., those with higher informational load) motivate hyper-articulation as well (e.g., (Jurafsky, Bell, Gregory, & Raymond, 2001)). These findings are compatible with the H&H theory's (Lindblom, 1990) prediction that sections of an utterance which bear a higher communicative load, such as high pragmatic load (strong-stance) and high informational load (high-surprisal), should be marked by increased hyper-articulation as the talker adjusts their speech to accommodate the assumed need of the interlocutor to recover the transmitted information. However, previous work has not explored the relative compounding effect of factors causing hyper- or hypo-articulation. In this study, we investigate the interaction between stance-taking and lexical surprisal using two measures of hyper-articulation, vowel space expansion and vowel duration. We use Generalized Additive Modeling to compare the effect of stance and surprisal on the repulsive force and duration of vowels, paying particular attention to the interaction of these factors.

Background Work

Lindblom's 1990 (Lindblom, 1990) H&H Theory drew on previous findings in the literature to propose an explanation for systematic variation in speech — talkers tend towards reduction when

there is sufficient context for the listener to recover the information in the utterance, but hyper-articulate when the communication demands it. In subsequent years, a variety of experimental and modeling findings have broadened our knowledge of and refined thinking around systematic variation in human speech and the underlying communicative contexts (e.g., Anderson, Bard, Sotillo, Newlands, & Doherty-Sneddon, 1997; Aylett & Turk, 2006; Baker & Bradlow, 2009; Katz & Selkirk, 2011; Tomita, 2008; Wright, 2004). As the picture has become fuller, more channels of situational information have been explored. In this context, we use the ATAROS corpus (Freeman et al., 2014) of dyadic problem-solving tasks to study the more thoroughly explored effects informational load, the less well-known effects of pragmatic load, and their interactions.

Methods

Dataset and Stance Annotation

We investigate these effects in English using the ATAROS dataset. This dataset contains dyadic conversations between 34 pairs of speakers on free-form collaborative tasks. We consider the inventory task (where dyads arrange inventory in a department store) and the budget task (where dyads balance the municipal budget of an invented county), totalling 116 recordings. We use the manually-annotated coarse stance labels provided in ATAROS (Freeman, 2015, pp. 16–18). Stance is defined on dimensions of strength (range 0-3, where 0 is the absence of stance-taking, and 3 is strong stance, discrete) and polarity (negative, neutral, or positive).

We consider all stressed vowels in content words.¹ Stress labels are taken

from dictionary pronunciations from the CMU pronouncing dictionary.² Word classes are tagged using the pre-trained Greedy Averaged Perceptron tagger from NLTK (Bird, Klein, & Loper, 2009).

Table 1 gives the counts of the stressed vowels in content words, grouped by stance type.

Table 1. Counts of vowel instances in the ATAROS dataset budget and inventory tasks, grouped by stance strength and polarity.

	–	Neutral	+
None	0	15374	0
Weak	403	19751	12064
Moderate	3749	15003	3344
Strong	282	341	51

Lexical Surprisal

We approximate the linguistic surprisal of speech with the lexical surprisal of a language model which has been trained on comparable data. Specifically, we train a Long Short-Term Memory network (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997), a neural network whose objective is to learn to predict the next word in a sequence of words. Parts 1 and 2 of the Fisher dataset (Cieri, Miller, & Walker, 2004) are used to train their model based on its similarity to the ATAROS dataset (both dyadic, spontaneous conversations). A model with hidden dimension 1024 and embedding dimension 50, using gradient clipping with a maximum norm of 1, is trained for 50 epochs with batch size 128. We use cross entropy loss with a weighted mean reduction as the training objective. A learning rate scheduler decreases the learning rate every 10 epochs, with multiplicative factor $\gamma = 0.1$. Once trained, this model can be used to associate probabilities to

¹ Specifically, we include the following Penn Treebank categories: ‘CD’, ‘FW’, ‘JJ’, ‘JJR’, ‘JJS’, ‘NN’, ‘NNS’, ‘NNPS’, ‘PDT’, ‘RB’,

‘RBR’, ‘RBS’, ‘UH’, ‘VB’, ‘VBD’, ‘VBG’, ‘VBN’, ‘VBP’, ‘VBZ.’

² <http://www.speech.cs.cmu.edu/cgi-bin/cmudict>

words in context.

The surprisal of a sentence with word sequence W is defined as the average log probability of the content words in the sequence, as produced by passing the entire sentence through the language model (Equation 1).

$$s(W) = -\frac{\sum_{w_{content} \in W} \log_2(p(w))}{|W|} \quad (1)$$

Repulsive Force Ratio

Following the adaptation of Lindblom’s gravitational force (Liljencrants, Lindblom, & Lindblom, 1972) found in McCloy, (2013); McCloy, Wright, & Souza, (2015); Wright, (2004), we categorize the relative expansion of the vowel space by considering the repulsive force of vowels relative to vowels produced by the same speaker. To compare the expansion of individual vowels rather than the vowel space in general, we modify the repulsive force employed in McCloy, (2013), normalizing by the average repulsive force of all instances of the same vowel.

Let l be the vowel index $l \in \{\Lambda, \upsilon, aI, u, ou, \ae, \varepsilon, i, \alpha, I, \text{ɜ}, \text{ɔ}, eI, au, \text{ɔ}I\}$ and for each vowel l (inscribed as a superscript), i is a single instance of the vowel $i = 1, \dots, n_l$ (inscribed as subscript), where n_l is the number of vowels with label l . A vowel instance v_i^l is represented by the mean F1 and F2 across its entire duration. Let $d(v_i^l, v_j^k)$ be the Euclidean distance between vowels v_i^l and v_j^k in the F1xF2 plane. The repulsive force $r(v_i^l)$ for the vowel instance v_i^l is the sum of the inverse square distances between v_i^l and all other vowel instances with a different label (Equation 2).

$$r(v_i^l) = \sum_{v_j^k, k \neq l} \frac{1}{d(v_i^l, v_j^k)^2} \quad (2)$$

Higher values of repulsive force correspond to greater degrees of phoneme overlap or encroachment, indicating hypoarticulation. Conversely, lower values indicate hyper-articulation.

The normalizing factor of repulsive force for vowel v_i^l is the average repulsive force for all vowels with the same label (Equation 3).

$$\bar{r}(v_i^l) = \frac{r(v_i^l)}{\sum_{v_j^k, k=l} r(v_j^l)} \quad (3)$$

Duration

We compute vowel duration from the timings from phone-level transcriptions force-aligned using the Penn Phonetics Lab Forced Aligner (P2FA, Yuan & Liberman, 2008). For comparability, we analyze all vowels that were included according to the criteria of the repulsive force ratio.

Statistical Comparison

We use Generalized Additive Modeling (Wood, 2017) as implemented in the ‘mgcv’ package (Wood, 2011) in R (using Gamma model family) to investigate the relationship between surprisal, stance-taking, and vowel space expansion and duration. This is a non-parametric modeling method, capable of modeling non-linear relationships between data which has been used in similar studies of acoustic distinctiveness (e.g., Kelley, 2021, p. 28 used a variant with mixed effects to study the impact of various acoustic measures on listener response times). In addition to stance and surprisal (smoothed via thin plate regression splines, Wood, 2003) variables, we include interactions between polarity and strength, and surprisal. We fit separate models for strength and polarity (both including surprisal and an interaction term).³ Neutral polarity, zero stance strength are treated as the intercept

³ In the syntax of mgcv, the formula that defines the model is `gam(repulsive force`

`| distance) ~ s(surprisal) + stance {polarity|strength} +`

conditions.

Results

Figure 1 shows the distributions of the repulsive force ratio and vowel duration for the vowels of interest.

Figure 1. Kernel density estimates of repulsive force ratio (blue) and duration (red).

Table 2. Summary of GAM linear stance strength coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting the repulsive force ratio, with and without interacting effects. Stance strength 0 is intercept. Only significant interactions included.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	1.011	***	1.011	***
	1	-.004	ns	-.004	ns
	2	-.028	***	-.028	***
	3	-.058	***	-0.56	**
EDF	srp	6.6	***	8.3	***
	srp.2	n/a		7.1	*
	srp.3	n/a		3.4	**

Table 3. Summary of GAM linear stance strength coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting duration, with and without interacting effects. Stance strength 0 is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	8.43	***	8.42	***
	1	0.52	***	0.54	***
	2	1.55	***	1.54	***

	3	1.20	***	1.16	ns
EDF	srp	8.8	***	7.8	ns

In tables where significance is reported we use the following notation: *** = $p < 0.001$, ** = $p < 0.01$, * = $p < 0.05$. Significance of parametric coefficients is derived from the Bayesian estimated covariance matrix of the parameter estimators. For smoothed parameters, the effective degrees of freedom (EDF) estimates the degree polynomial needed to fit each term, and the associated significance is derived from ANOVA tests.

Tables 2 and 3 summarize the estimated linear coefficients of stance strength and surprisal EDF when modeling repulsive force ratio and duration, respectively. The coefficients indicate the impact of the stance conditions on the predicted value (e.g., duration). Interaction terms are abbreviated with the syntax $srp.x$, where x is the stance condition. We compare models which include (right) and exclude (left) the interaction term. Tables 4 and 5 analogously report the coefficients and EDF of stance polarity-based models of repulsive force and duration, respectively.

Table 4. Summary of GAM linear stance polarity coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting the repulsive force ratio, with and without interacting effects. Stance polarity neutral (0) is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	1.000	***	1.011	***
	-	-.023	***	-.022	***
	+	-.005	*	-.005	*
EDF	srp	6.4	***	1.7	ns

Discussion

The statistical evidence supports previous findings that both pragmatic and informational load (operationalized as

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s(surprisal, by = stance {polarity|strength})
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stance-taking and surprisal) are sources of hyper-articulation, using quantitative measures repulsive force and duration.

Table 5. Summary of GAM linear stance polarity coefficients and surprisal (srp) function effective degrees of freedom (EDF) for predicting duration, with and without interacting effects. Stance polarity neutral (0) is intercept. No significant interactions.

Prediction Variables		- Interactions		+ Interactions	
		Est.	Sig.	Est.	Sig.
Coeff	0	9.33	***	9.34	***
	-	.16	ns	.10	ns
	+	-.88	***	-.84	***
EDF	srp	8.8	***	8.6	**

Without interactions, highly significant effects were found for stronger stance strength as well as surprisal for both repulsive force ratio and duration. Consistent with hyper-articulation, increasing stance reduces the repulsive force ratio and increases duration. When interaction terms are included in models with stance strength, they are only significant between surprisal and stronger stances (see Table 2). The inclusion of interaction terms can reduce the significance of other terms where there are interactions, i.e., between surprisal and strong stance. For duration, no interaction terms are significant, so including them leads to overfitting and reduces significance of strong stance which is associated with fewer instances.

In models without interaction terms, the most significant effects of stance polarity are: i) negative stance reduced repulsive force, consistent with hyper-articulation, and ii) positive stance reduced duration, consistent with hypo-articulation. This may be explained by the fact that most positive stance vowels are associated with weak stance taking, whereas most negative stance vowels are medium or strong stance levels. Surprisal is highly significant, but interaction terms are not useful and adding them reduces its significance.

The presence of significant interactions between surprisal and stronger levels of stance, but not polarity, provides new insight for the interpretation of competing motivations within the H&H framework.

Limitations and Future Work

These findings are representative of one slice of linguistic variation that may exist for informationally-marked or pragmatically-laden speech behaviours. It is not known whether similar interactions would be found for speakers of other languages or in other sociolinguistic contexts (e.g., in different cultural contexts or with familiar interlocutors).

In this work, vowel identity is not controlled for in the duration measure. This may have impacted the findings and is an area for future work.

Conclusion

We demonstrate that both stance-taking and linguistic surprisal significantly motivate changes in articulation, particularly in the gravitational force of the vowel space. Surprisal and stance-taking were found to interactively influence vowels' repulsive force. While both factors also affect vowel duration, the evidence for their interactions in this context is less definitive. These findings underscore the complex acoustic behaviors that result from competition in the H&H framework through different communicative needs.

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